

SELF-AWARENESS AND SELF-ESTEEM IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION: STRATEGIES
FOR DEVELOPING ADEQUATE ASSESSMENT OF PHYSICAL ABILITIES IN
ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT: This article examines the role of self-awareness and self-esteem in adolescent physical education. It analyzes the impact of an adequate perception of one's own physical capabilities on motivation, personal development, and success in mastering motor skills. Pedagogical strategies and methodological approaches aimed at developing a stable, realistic self-esteem in adolescents during physical education classes and extracurricular activities are presented. Psychological and pedagogical conditions that promote self-reflection, confidence, and self-acceptance are highlighted.

Key words: self-awareness, self-esteem, physical education, adolescents, motivation, personal development, pedagogical strategies.

In modern society, where health, physical development, and psychological well-being are central concerns, physical education is particularly important as a tool for developing a well-rounded personality. Adolescence is characterized by intense physical, emotional, and social development, making it a critical stage in the development of self-awareness and self-esteem.

It is during this age period that an individual's internal value system, self-perceptions, and understanding of their capabilities and limitations are actively developing. Physical activity provides unique conditions for these processes to manifest, as physical activity not only improves health but is also an important means of self-discovery and self-affirmation.

The effectiveness of physical education is largely determined by adolescents' awareness of their physical abilities and their desire for self-improvement. Adequate self-esteem becomes a factor in determining motivation, self-confidence, and willingness to cooperate. Therefore, developing self-awareness and fostering realistic self-esteem should be considered a strategic direction in modern physical education pedagogy.

1. The Importance of Self-Awareness and Self-Esteem in Physical Education

Self-awareness is a person's awareness of their qualities, capabilities, and goals, while self-esteem reflects their attitude toward these qualities. These psychological mechanisms are particularly evident in physical education: teenagers evaluate themselves through the prism of their physical achievements, compare their results with their classmates, and receive emotional feedback from their teachers.

Adequate self-esteem contributes to:

- development of internal motivation for sports;
- awareness of personal responsibility for results;
- formation of a sustainable interest in physical education.

On the contrary, over- or under-estimated self-esteem can lead to a refusal to engage in activities, a feeling of insecurity, or an overestimation of one's own abilities, which reduces the effectiveness of the educational process.

2. Factors influencing the formation of self-esteem

The main factors include:

Pedagogical influence - the teacher's communication style, the nature of feedback and methods of assessing achievements;

Social comparison is the perception of one's own results relative to the success of one's peers;

Personal characteristics - level of aspiration, emotional stability, motivation;

The learning environment is supportive, encouraging collaboration and mutual respect.

The development of adequate self-esteem is only possible in conditions of pedagogical support, where mistakes are seen as part of the learning process, and not as a defeat.

3. Pedagogical strategies for developing adequate self-esteem

The following approaches are effective for successfully developing self-awareness and self-esteem in physical education:

1. Reflective exercises – discussion with students of their own feelings, achievements and difficulties after completing motor tasks.

2. Setting personal goals is the formation of individual standards that are focused not on comparison with others, but on one's own progress.

3. Achievement portfolio – keeping a diary of your activities and successes, allowing you to see the dynamics of your growth.

4. Differentiated approach – taking into account individual physical capabilities during assessment.

5. Supportive feedback - focuses on effort and effort, not just results.

These strategies help develop intrinsic motivation, increase confidence, and foster a positive attitude toward physical activity.

4. Practical implementation

Integrated forms of work can be used within the school physical education program:

- game situations with elements of self-assessment (for example, "evaluate your result");
- mini-discussions after exercises ("what went better than yesterday?");
- self-analysis tests of physical fitness (on scales of endurance, flexibility and strength);
- project activities - creating your own mini-training programs.

Regular inclusion of such elements contributes to the formation of a reflective attitude towards physical development and strengthening of students' personal autonomy.

The development of self-awareness and adequate self-esteem in adolescents during physical education has profound psychological and pedagogical significance. A student's ability to objectively evaluate their own achievements determines not only their success in mastering motor skills but also their overall attitude toward physical activity, health, and personal growth.

Effective pedagogical support helps adolescents overcome self-doubt, fear of failure, and dependence on external assessments, fostering internal sources of motivation. Practical implementation of self-esteem development strategies—through reflection, support for individual achievements, and creating a context for success—builds trusting relationships between students and teachers, facilitating the development of personal potential.

With the digital transformation of education, opportunities for developing self-awareness are expanding. The use of digital monitoring tools, online diaries, fitness trackers, and interactive platforms can become an additional means of fostering adolescents' conscious attitudes toward physical development.

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Therefore, the development of adequate self-esteem should be considered as one of the key areas of modernization of the physical education system, ensuring sustainable personal development and motivation for a healthy lifestyle in the 21st century.

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